

Establishment of Appropriate Time Scale Resolution for Regional Drought Characterisation in Northern Nigeria

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Abstract

The increasing recurrence of extreme hydrological events, such as floods and droughts, has raised serious concerns among hydrologists. A major challenge in drought analysis is the lack of precise temporal resolution, which complicates its quantification. The subjectivity in selecting appropriate indicators and timescales has led to ongoing debates in drought assessment and management. This study employed a systematic approach involving (1) the computation and evaluation of drought patterns using the Standardised Precipitation Index (SPI) across multiple timescales and thresholds, and (2) the characterisation of drought properties through temporal accumulation (TA). Findings revealed that SPI-6 and SPI-9 are the most suitable timescales for drought characterization across northern Nigeria. Additionally, the optimal timescales for specific hydrological areas (HAs) were identified: HA 1 (SPI-6), HA 2 (SPI-6), HA 3 (SPI-3), HA 4 (SPI-6), and HA 8 (SPI-1). Threshold analysis indicated that a -1.0 SPI threshold consistently recorded the highest drought frequency (61 occurrences) across all TA considerations, making it the most effective for detecting minor drought events in the study region. Consequently, this threshold is recommended for comprehensive drought assessment in northern Nigeria. To enhance future drought analysis, it is suggested that persistence studies incorporate a renewal forgetting factor. Additionally, further research should explore the relationship between meteorological droughts and external climatic drivers, such as sea surface temperature (SST). The integration of machine learning techniques is also recommended to improve temporal accumulation assessments and overall drought modelling.

Keywords: Drought, Timescale, SPI, Nigeria

1. Introduction

Drought was qualified only by absolute measurement of rainfall amounts and dry spell duration. Latest understanding has moved the definitions towards an onset and cessation of rainfall according to duration of precipitation (Omonijo et al., 2014). The long period of drought in northern Nigeria in the seventies, eighties and nineties has been attributed to the persistence of a cyclonically and anti-cyclonic tropical air system within the atmosphere, which interrupts the normal upward movement of air during the mid-summer of the Hadley cell (Omonijo et al., 2014). The historical records indicates region in the northern parts of Nigeria where droughts have been reported to occurred more than once and had led to famine events such as those of 1903 and 1911-1914 (Shiru et al., 2018). Other significant occurrence of drought has taken place in 1919, 1924, and 1935, and 1951-1954 (Eze et al., 2018), with more recent events in 2007 and 2011 (Abaje et al., 2013). The situation is worsened by rapid population growth, overgrazing, farming, and poverty, all of which have made life hard for the affected communities (Eze, 2017). The dynamic nature of drought necessitated its proper characterisation in order to plan for water resource as well as inform the drought mitigation measures. Hence, this calls for continuous assessments of water availability compared with water demand and deficits in precipitation and water scarcity risks (Otache et al., 2020). There is an ambiguity in interpretation, in selecting appropriate drought identification methods, timescales, and indices can adequately describe drought patterns in both the spatial and temporal dimensions (Wilhite, 2000). However, determining the most suitable timescale for all drought scenarios or specific regions remains a challenge, as there is no universal standard. This highlights the importance of selecting an optimal timescale for drought quantification. According to Vicente-Serrano et al. (2010), timescale resolution is the period from which water deficits accumulate, that affects drought development. A major issue in the drought analysis is the subjective selection of

indicators and timescales, which has led to inconsistencies in past studies and management endeavours (Rodrigues et al., 1993). Chukwu (2024) as emphasises one of the primary challenges in drought characterisation was: finding a reliable time unit to serve as the best possible driver for assessment of drought. Jimoh et al. (2023) have pointedly mentioned that the selection of timescale choices is of considerable importance in the monitoring and comparative assessment of droughts; Rodrigues et al. (1993) state that the use of different time units, especially those less than a year, exert strong influences on time-scale resolution. The difficulty lies in finding a proper timescale resolution or temporal accumulation (TA) for the assessment of drought, because huge discretisation time units or time scale and in all likelihood may neglect macro-view trend in small discretisation temporal resolution also the other way round. In light of drought monitoring and quantifications, despite being so crucial, the resolution of timescale has remained neglected at same time under investigated. This research brought to fore key observations: (1) In the entire northern Nigeria, there is no established singular timescale for characterisation rather choice was based on individual intuition. (2) There is no study that has systematically identified the most appropriate timescale resolution for each of the hydrological areas in northern Nigeria, and no study has investigated the classification of drought occurrences in a given hydrological area as a function of timescale. (3) The review of the literature suggests that no universally accepted timescale or threshold for drought assessment has yet been established in northern Nigeria. (4) Furthermore, Zulfiqar et al. (2019) noted that the machine learning techniques have not been profoundly applied for the selection of suitable timescale resolution; hence, there is a need to explore this approach, in view of proffering solution to the prevailing issues. The past studies on hydro-climatic conditions in Nigeria, especially after the onset of the Sahelian drought in 1969, have concentrated on the socio-economic impacts of environmental degradation. Drought and

desertification, coupled with their causes and possible mitigation measures, have been studied. However, the characterising principles of drought and time step analysis have received little attention. Hence, this study was set to achieve the objective of establishing an appropriate timescale resolution for regional drought characterisation in northern Nigeria.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. Study location and data assembly

The studied area was positioned between latitudes 10°N and 14°N and longitudes 4°E to 7°5'E. Northern Nigeria is an area within the arid and semi-arid zones of Nigeria and is

mainly characterized by Sudanese vegetation. The area shares an unmistakable bi-seasonal pattern, with a very well-defined wet season and a dry season. The wet season stretches from April to October, while the dry season lasts from November to March (Jimoh et al., 2023). Figure 1 shows the hydrological areas (HAs) in northern Nigeria. For the purpose of this study, rainfall data for the last five decades (1971–2021) were analysed. Monthly average rainfall was considered as point-based rainfall data during the target periods. Rainfall data were collected from NIMET and River Basin Development Authority, Zonal Offices for Katsina, Kano, Minna, and Sokoto states.

Figure 1. Hydrological areas in Northern Nigeria

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Assessment of timescale resolution in drought phenomenon

2.2.1.1. SPI computation

To determine the Standardised Precipitation Index (SPI), the recorded precipitation totals were fitted to a gamma probability distribution.

SPI was computed for various accumulation periods, namely, SPI-1, SPI-3, SPI-6, SPI-9, SPI-12, SPI-24, and SPI-48. The parameters of a gamma distribution were first used to obtain an estimate of the cumulative probability from the observed dataset according to the method specified by Otache (2008). This method was carried out in the following way:

$$H(x) = q + (1-q) G(x) \tag{2}$$

where, q = probability of zero values and Z is the computed SPI values.

$$Z = \begin{cases} -[t - \frac{c_0+c_1t+c_2t^2}{1+d_1t+d_2t^2+d_3t^3}] & \text{for } 0 < H(x) \leq 0.5 \\ +[t - \frac{c_0+c_1t+c_2t^2}{1+d_1t+d_2t^2+d_3t^3}] & \text{for } 0.5 < H(x) < 1.0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$t = \begin{cases} \left[\ln \left(\frac{1}{(H(x))^2} \right) \right]^{1/2} & \text{for } 0 < H(x) < 0.5 \\ \left[\ln \left(\frac{1}{(1.0-H(x))^2} \right) \right]^{1/2} & \text{for } 0.5 < H(x) < 1.0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

2.2.1.2. Boruta algorithm and relative importance of timescales

Employing the Random Forest classification technique, an application in machine learning, Boruta's algorithm was used with R programming for the study. It makes use of the Random Forest package: adapter for normal permutation, adapter for raw permutation, and Gini importance statistics as classifiers. These lead towards identifying most stable and unbiased timescale resolution. Boruta treats spatial reference points of meteorological stations or homogeneous zones as response classes, whereas the temporal SPI across various timescales acts as predictor variables in line with Kurasa et al. (2010):

- To augment the data range of the system, multiple copies of all variables were available, which were kept with a five shadow minimum variable for each timescale for the series.
- Shadow variables randomized to break these features' correlation across timescales and the meteorological stations with spatial references.
- The entire dataset was passed through the Random Forest classifier and subsequently produced a Z-statistic, calculated from an average by dividing it with its standard deviation, thereby serves as importance measurement value.
- For each timescale, the Z-statistic was compared to the highest Z-statistic recorded among the shadow attributes.
- Each of the attributes that presented uncertainty in their classification was subjected to a two-sided significance testing procedure against the shadow attributes.
- Original timescales, found to be less significant than the shadow attributes, were

permanently excluded because they represented irrelevant variables during this stage as modelled by shadow attributes.

- These therefore confirmed the timescales over the shadow attributes as significant within themselves as the shadow attributes were reference points then for relevant variables.
- The shadow attributes were removed out of the system once all the relevant timescales were identified.
- This whole scheme was repeated several times, thus to assign weights to every timescale optimally. Ultimately, timescales that possessed significant Z scores statistically, above their shadow attributes was regarded as the most important and unbiased measures. On the other side, such timescales possessed lower Z scores than the shadow attributes and, therefore, was regarded as irrelevant and excluded from the system.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Drought characteristics and implication of timescale

3.1.1. Appropriate threshold for drought analysis

According to Table 1, the efficiency of three different thresholds (-1.0, -1.5, and -2.0) was assessed on various SPI temporal accumulation (TA) periods or timescales. The frequency of drought event occurrences was chosen as the criterion for judgment and subsequent conclusions. As shown by the station-based analysis outlined in Table 1, however, the threshold impacts across multiple TAs produced varying results. The results in Table 1 state that, on average, the occurrence of drought events is over 99% at the threshold of -1.0, whereas for -1.5 and -2.0, it drops to about 60%. This is in line with Zhang et al.

(2017) states that a preferable threshold must capture the most trivial or localised occurrences of drought. Therefore, this study regards -1.0 threshold as the most adequate threshold for identification of meteorological drought. This exceptionally gives high frequency of drought events at the said threshold and was able to explained the fact that all drought miniature cases were counted, which is a basis for effective water resources planning, assessment and monitoring as suggested Pei et al. (2020). Irrespective of the differentiating effects of mild, moderate, severe, or extreme drought status. On the other

hand, Wu et al. (2019) opined that critical threshold provides a robust estimation of the linkage between drought impacts associated with different types of drought. The drought frequency was at the highest at -1.0 threshold in all cases, and accounted for a total of 61 drought events through the entire spectrum of TA despite the reduction of data length caused by TAs. Therefore, the results in Table 1 emphasises that the -1.0 threshold is well recognised for identifying drought events even on a smaller scale. Sequel to the effectiveness of the -1.0 threshold, Table 2 shows the trend in drought frequency as a function of TA.

Table 1. Threshold analysis for various temporal accumulation

station	Threshold	SPI Temporal Accumulation							Average
		1	3	6	9	12	24	48	
Kaduna	-1.00	79	107	125	118	108	102	108	106.71
	-1.50	37	56	64	64	55	67	69	58.86
	-2.00	14	20	24	24	22	30	46	25.71
Kano	-1.00	80	83	101	114	111	125	127	105.86
	-1.50	45	40	53	62	66	75	68	58.43
	-2.00	19	12	16	23	21	5	0	13.71
Sokoto	-1.00	41	60	80	86	75	83	101	75.14
	-1.50	15	6	10	14	21	22	67	22.14
	-2.00	5	0	3	5	5	0	5	3.28
Lokoja	-1.00	59	68	70	74	80	78	72	71.57
	-1.50	16	27	31	28	26	78	37	34.71
	-2.00	8	8	10	5	5	9	6	7.286
Makurdi	-1.00	53	53	78	74	150	48	45	71.57
	-1.50	21	21	28	26	147	28	21	41.71
	-2.00	9	8	11	7	44	11	0	12.86
Bauchi	-1.00	24	38	51	59	59	64	46	48.71
	-1.50	11	13	26	25	23	23	28	21.29
	-2.00	8	8	11	9	11	7	13	9.57
Yola	-1.00	15	18	24	23	26	20	12	19.71
	-1.50	9	9	11	13	12	4	0	8.29
	-2.00	7	7	6	2	0	0	0	3.14
Katsina	-1.00	33	54	80	96	102	68	65	71.15
	-1.50	18	26	41	53	61	51	63	44.71
	-2.00	8	12	15	16	14	35	42	20.29
Maiduguri	-1.00	8	15	20	18	15	23	12	15.86
	-1.50	4	4	6	4	2	0	0	2.86
	-2.00	0	4	3	1	1	0	0	1.29
Jos	-1.00	22	21	11	25	24	8	24	19.29
	-1.50	22	10	2	15	18	6	12	12.14
	-2.00	4	4	0	2	1	0	0	1.57

It is inferred from the results that drought frequency increases initially when TA increases before stabilising at an optimal level. For most cases, across the study region, drought frequencies were escalated from a TA of 1 to TA 12 and gradually declined but rather consistent decrease typified by the average

values for TA 1 through to TA 48. The average duration of drought was around 47% per month between TA 1 and TA 6, while annual ranges from TA 6 to 48 had an average frequency of 66%. This indicates that TA 6 or TA 9 could be appropriate for meteorological drought assessment when using the -1.0 threshold. The

thrust of these findings is that both intermediate and longer time scales are effective in drought characterisation. These results are contrast with Wu et al. (2019b) in the analysis of SPI values of both 10 and 30 days. This situation could arise due to the heterogeneous patterns of rainfall with respect to space and time, which by variance affects the SPI ability to detect drought signals at a

specific timescale. SPI also varies in sensitivity across timescales, making analysis subjective, thus leading to different conclusions. Therefore, the most appropriate temporal resolution for SPI must lie on different characteristics in a given region of interest. Taking into consideration, climate change, ideal accuracy and reliability of the drought studies.

Table 2. Adopted threshold and summary statistics

Station	Threshold	SPI Temporal Accumulation						
		1	3	6	9	12	24	48
Kaduna		79	107	125	118	108	102	108
Kano		80	83	101	114	111	125	127
Sokoto	-1	41	60	80	86	75	83	101
Lokoja		59	68	70	74	80	78	72
Makurdi		53	53	78	74	150	48	45
Bauchi		24	38	51	59	59	64	46
Yola		15	18	24	23	26	20	12
Katsina		33	54	80	96	102	68	65
Maiduguri		8	15	20	18	15	23	12
Jos		22	21	11	25	24	8	24
Average		41.4	51.7	64	68.7	75	61.9	61.2

3.2. Application of boruta algorithm for determination of regional timescale

3.2.1. Normal permutation protocol

Statistical evaluation and performance assessment of normal permutation adapter across all considered HAs were exercised and are presented in Figure 1 and Table 3. Particularly as stated in Table 3 the SPI-6 was the most significant temporal scale of accumulation; the normal hit value of around 0.76 (or 76%) with a high mean importance score of 4.67, and a high importance score of 8.75, reconciles this criterion. The highest importance value was accorded to SPI-6 being the topmost performing scale rank when juxtaposed with all other timescales evaluated like SPI-1, SPI-3, SPI-9, SPI-12, SPI-24, and SPI-48. Whereas SPI-3 corroborated a relatively good performance falling behind SPI-6 on a level of 46% normal hit value with a mean score of importance of 2.78. Thus, with

this second however close classification, SPI-3 is considered the second most relevant timescale for HA 1. As supported by in Figure 2. On a grand scale, the timescales that were most frequently rated for almost the whole area of study, based on average normal hit percentages, were ranked as follows: SPI-6 (45%), SPI-9 (35%), SPI-3 (27%), SPI-48 (23%), SPI-12 (21%), and SPI-24 (21%). These findings corroborate the conclusions presented by Wu et al. (2019), which stated that short SPI timescales are effective in the characterisation of meteorological drought and, hence, agricultural drought. Intermediate timescales may also be applicable to the assessment of hydrological drought, remembering the fact that meteorological droughts invariable can transit into other drought types. This perspective becomes especially relevant when considering the role of climate changes.

Figure 2. Boxplot for normal permutation adapter of (a) HA1 (b) HA2 (c) HA3 (d) HA4 (e) HA8

Table 3. Distinctive Statistics of Norm Permutation across HAs

HA	TA	Statistics			Decision
		meanImp	maxImp	normHits	
1	1	-1.67	0.24	0.00	Rejected
	3	2.78	6.45	0.46	Tentative
	6	4.67	8.75	0.76	Confirmed
	9	1.28	4.96	0.25	Rejected
	12	1.66	4.23	0.19	Rejected
	24	1.35	4.35	0.21	Rejected
	48	0.44	1.80	0.02	Rejected
	1	1.77	5.67	0.39	Tentative
2	3	-0.91	0.51	0.00	Rejected
	6	5.74	11.76	0.89	Confirmed
	9	4.65	7.55	0.84	Confirmed
	12	0.38	2.89	0.02	Rejected
	24	4.67	8.18	0.86	Confirmed
	48	2.54	6.54	0.53	Tentative
	1	5.70	8.34	0.84	Confirmed
	3	5.84	10.02	0.88	Confirmed
3	6	1.99	4.96	0.12	Rejected
	9	4.03	7.43	0.66	Confirmed
	12	5.84	8.89	0.83	Confirmed
	24	0.37	2.28	0.00	Rejected
	48	3.47	6.37	0.60	Tentative
	1	1.85	5.59	0.03	Rejected
	3	-1.17	1.88	0.00	Rejected
	6	2.90	10.09	0.47	Tentative
4	9	0.69	2.37	0.00	Rejected
	12	0.71	3.54	0.01	Rejected
	24	-0.25	1.78	0.00	Rejected
	48	-0.14	0.91	0.00	Rejected
	1	3.59	9.37	0.55	Tentative
	3	-0.32	2.87	0.02	Rejected
	6	0.50	1.99	0.01	Rejected
	9	-0.04	2.21	0.02	Rejected
8	12	-1.93	-0.59	0.00	Rejected
	24	0.19	1.57	0.00	Rejected
	48	0.60	3.25	0.02	Rejected

3.2.2. Raw permutation adapter protocol

The Table 4 shows that the most significant temporal accumulation (TA) scale is SPI-6 that is, it had norm hit rates of 79%, and mean important of 5.91 for HA 1 and norm hit rates 90%, and mean important of 7.99 for HA 2. It is clear that drought in HA 1 and HA 2 can adequately be described via SPI-6. However, in the case of HA 2 SPI-9 seems to perform better than SPI-1 in HA 1. The difference between SPI-6 and SPI-9 performances in HA 2 was small and insignificant while much differences exist SPI-1 and SPI-6 in HA 1. For example, in terms of mean importance, maximum importance, and norm hit percent. Table 4 shows that 57.14% of the studied TA performed well, with three be the most noticed, thus in order of relevant as; SPI-

3 (89% norm hit, 12.65 mean important and 10.12 maximum important), SPI-1 (85% norm hit, 10.61 mean importance and 7.99 maximum importance) and SPI-12 (84% norm hit, 8.84 mean importance and 7.61 maximum importance). From Table 4 considering the entire region, the most frequent referenced TAs are SPI-6 (3 times), SPI-9 (3 times), SPI-1 (2 times), SPI-3 (2 times), SPI-12(1 time), SPI-24 (0) and SPI-48(0) with the average norm hits percent of SPI-1(30.7%), SPI-3(31.8%), SPI-6 (60.6%), SPI-9(45.9%), SPI-12(24.1%),SPI-24(22.5%) and SPI-48(23.0%). The implication of this is that, the lower TAs (3-9) seemed suitable for drought analysis. Short-term accumulation scales, lying between SPI-3 and SPI-9, thus produce the most optimal output for drought

assessment reflective both of agricultural and hydrological drought features as a predominant drought type in the whole northern Nigeria. Larger accumulation periods may blur

important drought signals, rendering them nearly imperceptible due to the eventual data reduction.

Table 4. Distinctive statistics of raw permutation across HAs

HA	TA	Statistics			Decision
		meanImp	maxImp	normHits	
1	1	1.97	0.24	0.00	Rejected
	3	2.81	6.45	0.46	Tentative
	6	4.67	8.75	0.76	Confirmed
	9	1.28	4.96	0.25	Rejected
	12	1.66	4.23	0.19	Rejected
	24	3.35	4.35	0.21	Rejected
	48	0.94	1.80	0.02	Rejected
	1	2.77	5.67	0.39	Tentative
2	3	0.91	0.51	0.00	Rejected
	6	4.54	10.76	0.89	Confirmed
	9	2.65	7.55	0.84	Confirmed
	12	0.38	2.89	0.02	Rejected
	24	4.67	8.18	0.86	Confirmed
	48	2.54	6.54	0.53	Tentative
	1	5.70	8.34	0.84	Confirmed
3	3	5.84	10.02	0.88	Confirmed
	6	1.99	4.96	0.12	Rejected
	9	4.03	7.43	0.66	Confirmed
	12	5.84	8.89	0.83	Confirmed
	24	0.37	2.28	0.00	Rejected
	48	3.47	6.37	0.60	Tentative
	1	1.85	5.59	0.03	Rejected
4	3	-1.17	1.88	0.00	Rejected
	6	2.90	10.09	0.47	Tentative
	9	0.69	2.37	0.00	Rejected
	12	0.71	3.54	0.01	Rejected
	24	-0.25	1.78	0.00	Rejected
	48	-0.14	0.91	0.00	Rejected
	1	3.59	9.37	0.55	Tentative
8	3	-0.32	2.87	0.02	Rejected
	6	0.50	1.99	0.01	Rejected
	9	-0.04	2.21	0.02	Rejected
	12	-1.93	-0.59	0.00	Rejected
	24	0.19	1.57	0.00	Rejected
	48	0.60	3.25	0.02	Rejected

3.2.3. Gini importance measure approach

As presented in Table 5 it was evidence that SPI-6 is the most appropriate temporal accumulation (TA) scale for both HA 1 and HA 8. Similar pattern were noticed in HA 4 and HA 8 were singular TA emerged as the best candidate TA that is SPI-6 and SPI-1 respectively. However, in ranking, SPI-6 came on top with a norm hit percentage of 92%, thus consolidating its position as the best probable TA for HA 2. The scenario was not similar for HA 3, where there were different TAs giving

closer results: SPI-1, SPI-3, SPI-9, and SPI-12; however, it was SPI-3 that gave the highest suitability for norm hit of 95%. Considering the frequency of TAs, across all the hydrological areas shows that SPI-6 occurs three times, while SPI-1 and SPI-9 occur twice in comparison. That, this TA was repeatedly present again suggested of it extreme important in drought analysis in region. In addition, give foregleam of transitional state dynamics of drought particularly from meteorological to streamflow drought in the whole northern Nigeria.

Table 5. Distinctive statistics of gini importance measure across Has

HA	TA	Statistics			Decision
		meanImp	maxImp	normHits	
1	1	-0.66	0.17	0.01	Rejected
	3	1.07	1.04	0.26	Rejected
	6	4.99	8.99	0.77	Confirmed
	9	1.00	2.86	0.25	Rejected
	12	1.00	2.33	0.15	Rejected
	24	1.05	2.22	0.21	Rejected
	48	0.64	1.10	0.01	Rejected
	1	0.61	2.20	0.02	Rejected
2	3	-0.70	0.31	0.00	Rejected
	6	7.51	11.88	0.92	Confirmed
	9	4.47	6.00	0.80	Confirmed
	12	0.12	1.41	0.01	Rejected
	24	4.99	8.54	0.83	Confirmed
	48	1.40	1.52	0.25	Rejected
	1	5.50	7.93	0.74	Confirmed
	3	9.01	14.72	0.95	Confirmed
3	6	0.05	1.00	0.00	Rejected
	9	4.71	7.90	0.67	Confirmed
	12	5.01	7.00	0.80	Confirmed
	24	0.06	2.22	0.00	Rejected
	48	-1.32	0.54	0.02	Rejected
	1	-0.56	1.71	0.03	Rejected
	3	1.11	0.17	0.01	Rejected
	6	10.22	8.37	0.73	Confirmed
4	9	1.92	5.15	0.39	Tentative
	12	1.01	2.17	0.20	Rejected
	24	1.41	1.12	0.06	Rejected
	48	-0.43	0.11	0.01	Rejected
	1	5.44	10.99	0.67	Confirmed
	3	-0.32	2.77	0.01	Rejected
	6	0.50	1.77	0.01	Rejected
	9	2.16	6.21	0.49	Tentative
8	12	-1.82	-0.67	0.00	Rejected
	24	0.18	1.67	0.00	Rejected
	48	0.61	3.25	0.02	Rejected

3.2.4. Selection of appropriate regional timescale resolution

Findings from this piece-wise analysis of normal and raw permutation, along with the Gini importance measure from the Boruta algorithm reveals the most suitable temporal accumulation (TA) or timescale pertinent to each hydrological area (HA) in northern Nigeria as inferred from Tables 6 and 7. From Table 6, it was observed that SPI-6 has an overall average percentage of 53.3% while SPI-9 closely followed with an average of 52% for the algorithms explored. Based on the evaluations contained in Tables 6, SPI-6 is the most appropriate TA for the whole northern Nigeria, while SPI-9 is the second best option. However, in performance and effectiveness, SPI-6 and SPI-9 almost overlap and can be used interchangeable. Nevertheless, for objectivity, SPI-6 is pegged as the best TA among others. In addition, Table 7, gives

adequate synopsis of suitable TA for any desirable HA and possibly second best. For examples, HA 1, HA 3 and HA 8 historical drought phenomena in this region can easily be analysis using SPI-6 and SPI-3, SPI-3 and SPI-1, SPI-1 and SPI-1 respectively. In line with the Findings of Chukwu (2024), time scale resolution or TA give thorough impression of preponderance of class or type of drought in a given region, whether is meteorological, agriculture or hydrological. In the light of the foregoing, Table 7 provided a basis for effective water resources planning and through insight into probable agricultural system adoptable in each HA as each TA reveals a particular drought signatures prevailing. For instance, HA 2 with appropriate time scale of SPI-6 and SPI-24, the implication is that the primary drought type roping that area was streamflow and reservoir deficiency that transit into groundwater deficiency for a protracted

long time. This area may probably be drain by intermittent, ephemeral and seasonal streams or basin. These streams shows great erratic pattern that transcend into groundwater regime. A trace of similarity may be visible in HA 1, 2 and 4 which constitute 60% of the entire region. However, Otache *et al.* (2020) contented that the primary input to any hydrological process is rainfall. Therefore, it is important to inferred that rainfall seasonality in northern Nigeria may have abruptly short change by unprecedented dry season that may have lingered beyond normal, this may have

accounted 60% shortage of streamflow and concomitant recharge process and rendered the area drought prone. However, agricultural activities and water resources management should be based on the expository espoused in this research. In the overall, there is seemingly preponderance of mixed grill of meteorological, agriculture and hydrological signatures and strong persistence in the drought series, this implies varying long-term memory scenario with attendance varying variance or heteroscedasticity.

Table 6. HAs probability ranking

TA	Normal	Raw	Gini
SPI-1	0%	40%	40%
SPI-3	0%	40%	20%
SPI-6	60%	60%	60%
SPI-9	40%	40%	40%
SPI-12	0%	20%	20%
SPI-24	20%	20%	20%
SPI-48	0%	0%	0%

Table 7. Summary of appropriate TA via HAs approach

HA	Suitability		Inference
	First	Second	
1	SPI-6	SPI-3	Streamflow and reservoir deficit/short and medium moisture deficit
2	SPI-6	SPI-24	Streamflow and reservoir deficit/groundwater deficit for long time scales
3	SPI-3	SPI-1	short and medium moisture deficit/short-term moisture deficit and crop stress
4	SPI-6	SPI-9	Streamflow and reservoir deficit/precipitation deficit over medium time scales
8	SPI-1	SPI-1	short-term moisture deficit and crop stress

4. Conclusions

Increased frequency of extreme hydrological events like floods and droughts has emerged as a critical issue in hydrology. One of the most significant issues involved in drought assessment is the data temporal resolution selection and its inherent uncertainties associated with it. Such subjective selection of indicators with time-scale resolutions often causes differences in drought analysis and management practices. To this end, the current study has optimally identified SPI-6 and SPI-9 as timescale of accumulation for drought characterisation over northern Nigeria. Appropriately, suitable timescale for different hydrological areas (HAs) within the region have also been found. For example, the chosen scales for HA 1, HA 2, HA 3, HA 4, and HA 8 are SPI-6, SPI-

6, SPI-3, SPI-6, and SPI-1, respectively. Of all comparisons made, a threshold of -1.0 across all instances resulted in the highest number of drought incidents (61), regardless of the reduction in data length which may result from shift in temporal scales. This concludes that the threshold met the requirement for minor drought events in the given study area, thus establishing it as the most relevant threshold for drought analysis within northern Nigeria and at such stands as an ideal timescale for assessment of drought phenomenon within the region.

Declaration of Author Contributions

S. E. Chukwu wrote the R programming code, statistical analysis and draft the results and discussion, M.Y. Otache conceived the project topic, designed and supervised the

entire research, J. J. Musa and P. O. Atemoagbo assisted in obtaining the data and wrote the introduction, methodologies and conclusions.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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